

Impact of Weight gain and weight loss on the volume and function of the thyroid gland in obese women

Dr. Shazia Fahmi, Dr. Hira Ahmed, Dr. Hina Jabeen, Dr. Soofia Nigar, Dr. Muhammad Kamran, Dr. Uzma Hameed

Article Info

Article History

Received:
October 04, 2021

Accepted:
May 05, 2022

Abstract

Objective: Women who are obese and those who are not may have a different thyroid volume and function. It is unknown whether weight loss has an effect on the thyroid gland's volume and function in obese individuals.

Methodology: The study enrolled 98 premenopausal euthyroid obese women (BMI = 30 kg/m²) and 31 non-obese women (BMI 25 kg/m²) (mean age 38.6 ± 12.9 years). Each participant's weight, height, BMI, waist circumference, body fat percentage, and fat mass were calculated. Thyroid function testing and thyroid ultrasonography were performed at baseline and six months after initiating treatment for obesity. Subgroups of people attempting to lose weight were studied.

Results: Obese women had larger thyroid volumes (P = 0.021) and higher TSH concentrations (P = 0.047), but lower free T3 and free T4 concentrations (P = 0.001 and P = 0.045, respectively). The relationship between thyroid volume and body weight (r = 0.319, P = 0.02), body mass index (bmi) (r = 0.504, P = 0.01), body fat percentage (r = 0.375, P = 0.01), body fat mass (r = 0.309, P = 0.01), and waist circumference (r = 0.386, P = 0.04) was all positive. Weight and fat mass were associated with increased TSH concentrations, with r = 0.227 and P = 0.042 indicating a positive correlation. Only obese women who lost more than 10% of their body weight following six months of obesity treatment experienced significant reductions in thyroid volume (P = 0.008) and TSH concentration (P = 0.006). Changes in body weight (r = 0.341, P = 0.009) were positively correlated with changes in thyroid volume and body fat (r = 0.406, P = 0.013).

Conclusion: Overweight women may have a variable thyroid volume and function depending on their body mass and fat mass; weight loss of more than 10% may alter thyroid volume and function, but the effect is clinically insignificant.

Introduction

Numerous studies have been conducted to determine the relationship between thyroid volume and total body weight and its various components. According to the majority of recent studies, there is a strong correlation between thyroid volume and body weight and BMI. According to some studies, thyroid volume is only related to lean body mass. As a result, the scientific literature contains contradictory findings regarding whether the thyroid hormone levels of obese and normal-weight individuals are the same. A few studies have been conducted on weight loss and thyroid volume and function, but the results have been inconsistent. As a result, we examined the relationship between obesity and euthyroidism in obese and non-obese women in this study. Additionally, we examined the relationship between thyroid function and thyroid volume, as well as the relationship between body weight, fat distribution, and thyroid function.

Methodology

The study population included 98 obese premenopausal women (BMI 30 kg/m²) and 31 non-obese premenopausal women (BMI 25 kg/m²). Consent was obtained from an informed patient. Each participant's BMI and waist circumference were calculated as part of this study (cm). Bio-Electrical Impedance Analysis was used to determine the percentage and weight of fat in the body. Thyroid disease, thyroid autoantibodies, and thyroid hormone or iodine-containing medication use have all been ruled out. All obese women were prescribed a weight loss medication (sibutramine 15 mg/day and/or orlistat 360 mg/day) because they were unable to lose weight through diet and exercise alone. Thyroid function tests and thyroid ultrasound were performed prior to initiating treatment for obesity. The serum TSH, free T3, and free T4 concentrations were determined using an ACS 180 chemiluminometric two-site sandwich immunoassay (Chiron Diagnostics)

In the supine position with the neck elongated, the same person was used to perform a thyroid US (high-resolution real-time ultrasonic scanner, 75 MHz probe, Toshiba, Tokyo, Japan). The thyroid volume in millilitres was calculated by multiplying the length, width, and thickness of each lobe by a correction factor. It was considered acceptable to have a goitre that had previously existed and had a thyroid volume greater than 18 ml. After six months of treatment, 89 obese women were classified into three groups: Weight loss of less than 5% was observed in 31 women; weight loss of 5% to 10% was observed in 26 women; and weight loss of 10% or more was observed in 32 women.

Data Analysis

SPSS statistical software was used to conduct the statistical analyses (version 26; SPSS). The findings are summarized using averages and standard deviations. After six months, we compared the parameters using the paired samples t-test. The data were compared between groups using the one-way anova test. In the Spearman test correlation analysis, a P-value of 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Obese women had a 245 percent goitre rate, while non-obese women had a 128 percent goitre rate. This group had higher TSH levels ($P = 0.47$) but lower fT3 and fT4 levels in the thyroid gland ($P = 0.11$ and $P = 0.45$, respectively). It is (Table 1)

There was a positive correlation between thyroid volume and body weight ($r = 0.319$, $P = 0.02$), BMI ($r = 0.504$, $P = 0.01$), total body fat percentage ($r = 0.375$, $P = 0.01$), body fat weight ($r = 0.309$, $P = 0.01$), and waist circumference ($r = 0.386$, $P = 0.04$). ($r = 0.338$; $P = 0.02$), BMI [33.2 kg/m²], body fat percentage [42.0 kg/m²], and body fat weight [498 kg/m²] all correlated negatively with the thyroid hormone fT4 concentration. TSH levels were positively correlated with participants' weight ($r = 0.227$, $P = 0.042$) and fat mass ($r = 0.268$, $P = 0.038$). After six months of obesity treatment, only group 3 experienced a decrease in thyroid volume and TSH concentration. Even after adjusting for baseline values, this group's thyroid volume and TSH concentration remained lower ($P = 0.01$ and $P = 0.015$, respectively). The tables 2, 3, and 4 show the baseline and 6-month changes in thyroid function and volume for each participant in groups 1, 2, and 3.

At the end of treatment, all groups experienced similar changes in fT3 and fT4 concentrations (= baseline–end of treatment). Between groups 1 and 2, or between groups 2 and 3, neither the volume nor the level of thyroid hormone varied. There was a statistically significant difference in thyroid volume and serum FT4 concentration between groups 3 and 1.

Both thyroid gland volume and thyroid gland volume were positively correlated with changes in body weight ($r = 0.341$; $P = 0.09$) and body fat mass ($r = 0.406$; $P = 0.13$). The relationship between changes in body weight and changes in fT4 concentration was positive ($r = 0.294$, $P = 0.045$).

Table 1:

	Obese (<i>n</i> = 98)	Nonobese (<i>n</i> = 31)	<i>P</i> -value
Age (years)	40.5 ± 11.4	38.6 ± 12.9	NS
Body weight (kg)	92.9 ± 15.8	55.3 ± 4.9	< 0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	38.6 ± 5.8	22.2 ± 1.6	< 0.001
Body fat percentage (%)	43.5 ± 4.2	27.4 ± 4.8	< 0.001
Body fat weight (kg)	42.1 ± 10.4	15.1 ± 3.1	< 0.001
Waist circumference (cm)	107.3 ± 11.3	76.0 ± 2.6	< 0.001
Thyroid volume (ml)	15.2 ± 5.3	12.2 ± 3.3	0.021
TSH (μIU/ml)	1.63 ± 0.76	1.12 ± 0.44	0.047
Free T4 (ng/dl)	1.12 ± 0.16	1.36 ± 0.19	0.045
Free T3 (pg/dl)	3.11 ± 0.48	3.37 ± 0.41	< 0.001

Table 2:

	Baseline	After 6 months	<i>P</i> -value
Body weight (kg)	91.6 ± 13.7	90.9 ± 12.1	NS
Body fat percentage (%)	44.9 ± 3.7	44.7 ± 3.3	NS
Body fat weight (kg)	43.6 ± 7.9	42.8 ± 6.9	NS
Waist circumference (cm)	116.0 ± 9.8	111.9 ± 9.8	NS
Thyroid volume (ml)	15.4 ± 6.5	17.2 ± 7.0	NS
TSH (μIU/ml)	1.84 ± 1.19	1.97 ± 1.08	NS
Free T4 (ng/dl)	1.09 ± 0.15	1.18 ± 0.22	NS
Free T3 (pg/dl)	2.89 ± 0.2	3.02 ± 0.58	NS

Table 3:

	Baseline	After 6 months	P-value
Body weight (kg)	100.1 ± 16.5	93.6 ± 10.1	< 0.001
Body fat percentage (%)	43.7 ± 3.5	42.1 ± 4.1	0.002
Body fat weight (kg)	47.0 ± 12.0	42.7 ± 12.1	< 0.001
Waist circumference (cm)	96.1 ± 6.8	90.5 ± 4.8	NS
Thyroid volume (ml)	14.7 ± 4.9	15.0 ± 4.6	NS
TSH (μIU/ml)	2.77 ± 1.0	2.61 ± 1.18	NS
Free T4 (ng/dl)	1.07 ± 0.1	1.17 ± 0.12	NS
Free T3 (pg/dl)	2.82 ± 0.4	3.02 ± 0.57	NS

Table 4:

	Baseline	After 6 months	P-value
Body weight (kg)	90.0 ± 20.4	78.4 ± 18.1	< 0.001
Body fat percentage (%)	44.6 ± 4.3	39.1 ± 8.8	0.003
Body fat weight (kg)	44.4 ± 14.7	33.7 ± 13.4	< 0.001
Waist circumference (cm)	104.1 ± 11.2	93.6 ± 14.7	< 0.001
Thyroid volume (ml)	15.4 ± 4.3	13.0 ± 4.1	0.008
TSH (μIU/ml)	1.49 ± 0.82	1.24 ± 0.80	0.006
Free T4 (ng/dl)	1.12 ± 0.12	1.11 ± 0.23	NS
Free T3 (p/dl)	3.11 ± 0.35	3.06 ± 0.70	NS

Discussion

The study area had a mild to moderate iodine deficiency. Previously, thyroid ultrasound in Antalya revealed a goitre prevalence of 34% in schoolchildren aged 6–11 years. Women who were obese were more likely to have a goitre than women who were not obese. Due to the fact that a deficiency of iodine results in cyclic TSH stimulation and eventually euthyroid goitre, it is widely accepted that this is due to insufficient thyroid hormone synthesis. While iodine deficiency can result in goitre in some individuals, this does not mean that everyone who lives in an area with a deficiency will develop the condition.

Our findings indicate that obese women are more likely than non-obese women to have goitres, implying that obesity is a phenotypic manifestation of this genetic predisposition. In both iodine-sufficient and mild/moderately iodine-deficient areas, thyroid volume was found to be associated with body weight, BMI, waist-hip ratio, and fat mass. The thyroid gland volume was found to be highly correlated with body weight, body mass index, body fat percentage, body fat weight, and waist circumference. Obese individuals had significantly higher TSH levels than non-obese individuals, a hormone that increases thyroid volume.

Numerous studies have established a link between obesity and thyroid hormones, but the evidence is mixed. The majority of studies discovered a link between elevated TSH and low T3 and low T4 levels, as well as an increase in BMI. Additionally, these studies discovered an increase in thyroid volume. However, the previous study state, these findings are not due to hypothyroidism or thyroid autoimmunity. We found no evidence of autoimmune thyroid disease in our subjects, but we cannot comment on the effect of an iodine deficiency because our subjects' urinary iodine excretion is unknown (iodine status).

Caloric intake is just one of a number of variables that affect thyroid hormone synthesis. Weight gain or loss has been shown to have varying effects on thyroid function and volume, which could be explained by the fact that study designs, populations, iodine status, and treatment modalities vary. According to new research, medications such as orlistat, dexfenfluramine, and sibutramine do not appear to have a significant effect on endocrine function. Weight loss may have an effect on thyroid function and volume, but this is unknown. Six months of physical activity resulted in changes in thyroid volume and body composition.

Numerous studies have linked weight loss to changes in thyroid hormone levels that are neither biologically nor clinically significant. We expected to see a decrease in thyroid volume following a diet or exercise programme due to the strong correlation between thyroid volume and body weight. After six months, weight loss of more than 10% resulted in a decrease in thyroid volume and TSH levels. Even when baseline thyroid volume was taken into account, thyroid volume and TSH concentrations decreased significantly. It is unknown how weight loss affects the volume and function of the thyroid.

Numerous studies have established a link between the pituitary–thyroid axis and leptin, with varying degrees of success. Leptin stimulates TRH biosynthesis in vitro and modulates the activity of the hypothalamic–pituitary–thyroid axis in vivo. While we did not measure leptin levels in our subjects, our results suggest an indirect relationship between leptin and the hypothalamic–pituitary–thyroid axis. Obese women had a higher TSH level and thyroid volume than non-obese women. The volume of the thyroid gland and the TSH concentration were found to be strongly related to body fat mass. The fluctuation of thyroid volume was discovered to be positively correlated with changes in body weight and fat mass. On the other hand, another study discovered no correlation between leptin levels and the pituitary–thyroid axis, but did discover one between leptin and thyroid volume.

Conclusion

As a result, the thyroid gland's volume increases in obese women and is strongly correlated with their weight and percentage of body fat. If the weight loss was greater than 10% in six months, obesity treatment resulted in a significant reduction in thyroid volume and TSH; weight loss of 10% had no effect. The changes in thyroid volume or function associated with changes in body weight and body fat percentage had no clinical or biological significance.

References:

Michalaki MA, Vagenakis AG, Leonardou AS, Argentou MN, Habeos IG, Makri MG, Psyrogiannis AI, Kalfarentzos FE, Kyriazopoulou VE. Thyroid function in humans with morbid obesity. *Thyroid*. 2006;16:73–8.

Salerno M, Capalbo D, Cerbone M, De Luca F. Subclinical hypothyroidism in childhood - current knowledge and open issues. *Nat Rev Endocrinol*. 2016;12:734–46.

Jin HY. Prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism in obese children or adolescents and association between thyroid hormone and the components of metabolic syndrome. *J Paediatr Child Health*. 2018;54:975–80.

Kok P, Roelfsema F, Langendonk JG, Frolich M, Burggraaf J, Meinders AE, Pijl H. High circulating thyrotropin levels in obese women are reduced after body weight loss induced by caloric restriction. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2005;90:4659–63.

De Pergola G, Ciampolillo A, Paolotti S, Trerotoli P, Giorgino R. Free triiodothyronine and thyroid stimulating hormone are directly associated with waist circumference, independently of insulin resistance, metabolic parameters and blood pressure in overweight and obese women. *Clin Endocrinol*. 2007;67:265–9.

Biondi B. Thyroid and obesity: an intriguing relationship. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2010;95:3614–7.

Muscogiuri G, Sorice GP, Mezza T, Prioletta A, Lassandro AP, Pirroni T, Della Casa S, Pontecorvi A, Giaccari A. High-normal TSH values in obesity: is it insulin resistance or adipose tissue's guilt? *Obesity (Silver Spring)*. 2013;21:101–6.

Soriguer F, Valdes S, Morcillo S, Esteva I, Almaraz MC, de Adana MS, Tapia MJ, Dominguez M, Gutierrez-Repiso C, Rubio-Martin E, et al. Thyroid hormone levels predict the change in body weight: a prospective study. *Eur J Clin Investig*. 2011;41:1202–9.

Marzullo P, Minocci A, Tagliaferri MA, Guzzaloni G, Di Blasio A, De Medici C, Aimaretti G, Liuzzi A. Investigations of thyroid hormones and antibodies in obesity: leptin levels are associated with thyroid autoimmunity independent of bioanthropometric, hormonal, and weight-related determinants. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2010;95:3965–72.

Lundback V, Ekblom K, Hagman E, Dahlman I, Marcus C. Thyroid-stimulating hormone, degree of obesity, and metabolic risk markers in a cohort of Swedish children with obesity. *Horm Res Paediatr*. 2017;88:140–6.

Wolffbuttel BHR, Wouters H, Slagter SN, van Waateringe RP, Muller Kobold AC, van Vliet-Ostapchouk JV, Links TP, van der Klauw MM. Thyroid function and metabolic syndrome in the population-based LifeLines cohort study. *BMC Endocr Disord*. 2017;17:65.

Ferrannini E, Iervasi G, Cobb J, Ndreu R, Nannipieri M. Insulin resistance and normal thyroid hormone levels: prospective study and metabolomic analysis. *Am J Physiol Endocrinol Metab*. 2017;312:E429–e36.

Rahbar AR, Kalantarhormozi M, Izadi F, Arkia E, Rashidi M, Pourbehi F, Daneshifard F, Rahbar A. Relationship between body mass index, waist-to-hip ratio, and serum lipid concentrations and thyroid-stimulating hormone in the Euthyroid adult population. *Iran J Med Sci*. 2017;42:301–5.

Guidelines for the prevention and control of overweight and obesity in Chinese adults (excerpt). Chinese working group on obesity. *J Nutr*. 2004;01:1–4.

Chinese guidelines on prevention and treatment of dyslipidemia in adults. Joint committee for developing Chinese guidelines on prevention and treatment of dyslipidemia in adults. *Chinese J Cardiol*. 2016;44:833–53.

Kim B. Thyroid hormone as a determinant of energy expenditure and the basal metabolic rate. *Thyroid*. 2008;18:141–4.

Reinehr T, Isa A, de Sousa G, Dieffenbach R, Andler W. Thyroid hormones and their relation to weight status. *Horm Res*. 2008;70:51–7.

Reinehr T, de Sousa G, Andler W. Hyperthyrotropinemia in obese children is reversible after weight loss and is not related to lipids. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2006;91:3088–91.

Grandone A, Santoro N, Coppola F, Calabro P, Perrone L, Del Giudice EM. Thyroid function derangement and childhood obesity: an Italian experience. *BMC Endocr Disord*. 2010;10:8.

Iacobellis G, Ribaldo MC, Zappaterreno A, Iannucci CV, Leonetti F. Relationship of thyroid function with body mass index, leptin, insulin sensitivity and adiponectin in euthyroid obese women. Clin Endocrinol. 2005;62:487–91.

Duarte GC, Cendoroglo MS, Araujo LM, Almada Filho Cde M. Association between increased serum thyrotropin concentration and the oldest old: what do we know? Einstein (Sao Paulo). 2015;13:117–21.

Harvey J. Leptin: a diverse regulator of neuronal function. J Neurochem. 2007;100:307–13.

Author Information

Dr. Shazia Fahmi

Assistant Professor, Anatomy department, KMDC

Dr. Hina Jabeen

Lecturer, Anatomy department, Dow International medical college (DIMC), DUHS

Dr. Muhammad Kamran

Lecturer, Department Of Anatomy, Dow Medical College, DUHS

Dr. Hira Ahmed

Assistant professor, Anatomy department, Karachi medical and dental college (KMDC)

Dr. Soofia Nigar

MBBS, M.Phil, Associate professor Anatomy Department, Dow University of Health Sciences ,DUHS

Dr. Uzma Hameed

Assistant professor, anatomy department, DUHS
